

Kinetics and mechanism of the ruthenium(III) catalyzed oxidation of some polyhydric alcohols by acid bromate

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Abstract : Ruthenium(III) catalyzed oxidation of some polyhydric alcohols *d*-sorbitol and *d*-mannitol by acidic solution of potassium bromate in the presence of mercuric acetate as a scavenger for Br⁻ ion have been made in the temperature range 30–45 °C. The reactions exhibit zero-order rate dependence with respect to each polyhydric alcohol and first order at low concentration range of KBrO₃ was observed to tend to zero at its higher concentrations. A suitable mechanism consistent with the experimental results has been proposed.

Keywords : Ruthenium(III), polyhydric alcohols, oxidation.

In continuation of our earlier work on the oxidation of amino acids^{1,2}, cyclic alcohols³, cyclic ketones⁴, glycerol⁵ and maltose⁶ by potassium bromate in acidic as well as alkaline media in the present investigation we have presented our study on "Ruthenium(III) catalyzed oxidation of some polyhydric alcohols by acid bromate".

Experimental

Aqueous solution of polyhydric alcohols (Thomas Baker), potassium bromate (s.d. fine Chem. Ltd.), sodium perchlorate and mercuric acetate (E. Merck) were prepared by dissolving the weighed amount of sample in triple distilled water. Ruthenium(III) chloride (Johnson Matthey) was prepared by dissolving the sample in hy-

drochloric acid of known strength. All other reagents were of analytical grade. Ionic concentration was maintained with NaClO₄.

Temperature was maintained to within ±0.1 °C of the desired value. A measured volume of potassium bromate solution, maintained at the same temperature, was rapidly poured into the reaction vessel. The kinetics was followed by examining aliquot portions of reaction mixture for potassium bromate iodometrically using starch as indicator after suitable-time intervals.

Results

Table 1 shows the stoichiometric results which reveal that two moles of bromate were consumed per mole oxida-

Table 1. Stoichiometric results for oxidation of *d*-sorbitol and *d*-mannitol

[Ru^{III}]_T = 9.60 × 10⁻⁶ M, [HClO₄] = 1.00 × 10⁻³ M, [KCl] = 1.00 × 10⁻³ M,
[Hg(OAc)₂] = 1.25 × 10⁻³ M, temp. = 323 K, time = 48 h, [BrO₃⁻]^{*} = [BrO₃⁻] left unconsumed after 48 h, [BrO₃⁻]^c = [BrO₃⁻] - [BrO₃⁻]^{*}
i.e. oxidant consumed during the reaction

10 ³ [BrO ₃ ⁻]	10 ² [Substrate]	10 ³ [BrO ₃ ⁻] [*] M (residual)		[BrO ₃ ⁻] ^c /[substrate]	
		<i>d</i> -Sorbitol	<i>d</i> -Mannitol	<i>d</i> -Sorbitol	<i>d</i> -Mannitol
<i>M</i>	<i>M</i>				
15.00	1.00	12.94	13.10	2.06	1.90
10.00	1.00	8.02	7.90	1.98	2.10
5.00	1.00	2.94	3.06	2.06	1.94
2.50	1.00	0.46	0.52	2.04	1.98
15.00	2.00	11.12	10.96	1.94	2.02
15.00	3.00	9.08	9.04	1.97	1.99
15.00	4.00	7.02	6.94	1.99	2.01
15.00	5.00	4.92	5.00	2.02	2.00

tion of polyhydric alcohols. The product analysis by spotting techniques indicates the presence of monocarboxylic acid in the reaction mixture after the reaction. So the product of oxidation should be monocarboxylic acids. The corresponding monocarboxylic acid (*d*-gluconic acid and *d*-mannonic acid respectively) were detected by conventional methods¹⁹.

Table 2 records the rate constants at different bromate and substrate concentrations. The reaction was observed to be independent of [substrate] as nearly constant *k* val-

ues are obtained on varying concentration of polyhydric alcohols which signifies zero order kinetics with respect to both *d*-sorbitol and *d*-mannitol. The kinetics recorded at various [Ru^{III}], ionic strengths of the medium along with kinetic effects on successive addition of mercuric acetate and sodium perchlorate are given in Table 2. First order dependence on [Ru^{III}] is evident from the close resemblance between the slope value (2.38×10^{-2} and $5.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 35 °C and 45 °C respectively for *d*-sorbitol and 2.66×10^{-2} and $5.33 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 35 °C

Table 2. Effect of variation of reactants on the reaction rate $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}} = 9.6 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$

[Bromate] $\times 10^3 \text{ M}$	[Substrate] $\times 10^2 \text{ M}$	[HClO ₄] $\times 10^3 \text{ M}$	[KCl] $\times 10^3 \text{ M}$	[NaClO ₄] $\times 10^3 \text{ M}$	[Hg(OAc) ₂] $\times 10^3 \text{ M}$	10 ⁷ <i>k</i> at 35 °C	
						<i>d</i> -Sorbitol	<i>d</i> -Mannitol
0.80	0.50	1.00	1.00	-	1.25	1.80	1.92
1.00	0.50	1.00	1.00	-	1.25	2.25	2.50
1.25	0.50	1.00	1.00	-	1.25	2.78	3.58
1.67	0.50	1.00	1.00	-	1.25	3.66	4.08
2.50	0.50	1.00	1.00	-	1.25	3.72	4.14
3.33	0.50	1.00	1.00	-	1.25	3.68	4.04
1.00	0.33	1.00	1.00	-	1.25	2.10	2.77
1.00	0.40	1.00	1.00	-	1.25	2.16	2.25
1.00	0.67	1.00	1.00	-	1.25	2.12	2.60
1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	-	1.25	2.30	2.75
1.00	2.00	1.00	1.00	-	1.25	2.20	2.50
1.00	0.50	0.8	1.00	-	1.25	2.34	2.25
1.00	0.50	1.25	1.00	-	1.25	2.44	2.42
1.00	0.50	1.67	1.00	-	1.25	2.40	2.56
1.00	0.50	2.50	1.00	-	1.25	2.30	2.32
1.00	0.50	5.00	1.00	-	1.25	2.24	2.53
1.00	0.50	1.00	0.8	-	1.25	2.00	2.22
1.00	0.50	1.00	1.25	-	1.25	2.25	2.50
1.00	0.50	1.00	1.67	-	1.25	2.66	2.82
1.00	0.50	1.00	2.50	-	1.25	3.05	3.14
1.00	0.50	1.00	5.00	-	1.25	3.34	3.50
1.00	0.50	1.00	1.00	-	1.25	3.68	3.92
1.00	0.50	1.00	1.00	0.80	1.25	2.71	2.20
1.00	0.50	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.25	2.61	2.42
1.00	0.50	1.00	1.00	1.25	1.25	2.30	2.10
1.00	0.50	1.00	1.00	1.67	1.25	2.40	2.32
1.00	0.50	1.00	1.00	2.50	1.25	2.57	2.34
1.00	0.50	1.00	1.00	5.00	1.25	2.33	2.22
1.00	0.50	1.00	1.00	-	0.80	2.09	2.11
1.00	0.50	1.00	1.00	-	1.00	2.00	2.25
1.00	0.50	1.00	1.00	-	1.67	2.10	2.40
1.00	0.50	1.00	1.00	-	2.50	2.20	2.10
1.00	0.50	1.00	1.00	-	5.00	2.34	2.32

and 45 °C respectively for *d*-mannitol oxidations) of k vs $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$ plot (Fig. 1) and average of experimental k_1 values 2.34×10^{-2} and $4.68 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 35 °C and 45 °C for *d*-sorbitol and 2.60×10^{-2} and $5.2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 35 °C and 45 °C for *d*-mannitol. Variation in concentration

Fig. 1. Plot between $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] \times 10^6 \text{ M}$ and $(-dc/dt) \times 10^7 \text{ ML}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for the oxidation of *d*-sorbitol at 35 °C (a) and at 45 °C (a') and of *d*-mannitol at 35 °C (b) and at 45 °C (b').

of hydrogen ions did not influence the value of k appreciably, showing thus zero-order kinetics in $[\text{H}^+]$ ions (Table 2). Negligible effect of variation in ionic strength of the medium and addition of mercuric acetate on the reaction rate was obvious from the kinetic data in Table 2. Kinetic results obtained on varying the concentrations of chloride ions indicate a positive effect of chloride ion variation. Change in the ionic strength has only a marginal effect.

The rate measurement were taken at 30–45 °C and specific rate constants were used to draw a plot of $\log(k_1)$ versus $1/T$ (Fig. 2). The values of energy of activation (ΔE^*), Arrhenius factor (A), entropy of activation (ΔS^*) and free energy of activation (ΔG^*), were calculated from the rate measurement at 30, 35, 40 and 45 °C and these values have been recorded in Table 3.

The negligible effect of mercuric acetate excludes the possibility of its involvement either as a catalyst or as an oxidant because it does not help the reaction proceed without bromate. Hence the function of mercuric acetate is to act as scavenger²⁰ for any Br^- ion formed in the reaction. It helps to eliminate the parallel oxidation by Br_2 , which would have been formed as a result of inter-

Fig. 2. Plot between $\log(k)$ and $1/T \times 10^4$ for the oxidation of *d*-sorbitol (a) and *d*-mannitol (b).

$[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] = 9.60 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$, $[\text{KCl}] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$,
 $[\text{HClO}_4] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2] = 1.25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$,
 $[\text{KBrO}_3] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[d\text{-Sorbitol}] = 0.50 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$,
 $[d\text{-Mannitol}] = 0.50 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$

Table 3. Activation parameters and values of k_2 for acid bromate oxidation of polyhydric alcohols

$[\text{HClO}_4] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{KCl}] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$,
 $[\text{KBrO}_3] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2] = 1.25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$,
 $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] = 9.60 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$, $[d\text{-Sorbitol}] = 0.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$,
 $[d\text{-Mannitol}] = 0.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$

Different temp. (°C)	$k \times 10^4 \text{ ML}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	$k \times 10^4 \text{ ML}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
	<i>d</i> -Sorbitol	<i>d</i> -Mannitol
30	1.58	1.62
35	2.25	2.50
40	3.10	3.54
45	4.46	5.08

Arrhenius parameters :

ΔE^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	55.847	63.833
$\log A$	9.8197	11.219
ΔS^* (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-14.502	-8.121
ΔG^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	74.607	74.338
ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	70.140	71.836

at 35 °C

Sl. no.	Substrate	1/[Rate] versus 1/[Cl]		Value of $\frac{[10^3 k_{-1} + k_2 + k_1]}{k_1 k_2}$
		Value of intercept	Value of k_2	
1.	<i>d</i> -Sorbitol	0.17×10^7	61.2	2.514×10^{-2}
2.	<i>d</i> -Mannitol	0.21×10^7	49.6	1.866×10^{-2}

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